

S I N G L E

D8.3 Data Management Plan – version 1

WP8, T8.4

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Technical references

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Executive summary

This deliverable report is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SINGLE project. The DMP aims to build a common ground for the scientific data handling and long-term use of all data generated during SINGLE project. The DMP follows the FAIR principles and will handle two different categories of data:

- Sensitive data will be stored in a private information space (SINGLE SharePoint) with access limited to partners within the consortium.
- Non-sensitive data will be placed in the open data repository Zenodo.

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

v	Date	Author(s)	Description
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1.0	13/11/2023	Selene Hernández Morejudo (CTMS), Veronica Meneghello (ICONS)	Final version

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to outline the strategies and methodologies for handling of data during the execution of the SINGLE project. This plan delineates the types of data that will be generated, outlines the project's intentions regarding data utilization, verification, and sharing, and provides a roadmap for long-term preservation. The document will be updated in M33 (DMP – version 2) to adjust it to the typology of the data collected and the uses identified by the consortium.

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2. SINGLE Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will handle two different categories of data: sensitive and non-sensitive data. Sensitive data will be stored in a private information space (SINGLE SharePoint) with access limited to partners within the consortium. Non-sensitive data will be placed in an open data repository.

2.1. SINGLE SharePoint

A SINGLE SharePoint site has been created for internal access to the partners (see deliverable D8.1). Data from the SINGLE project will be stored in a SharePoint project site. This will be the projects' working and collaboration area during 36 months of active project period. Every partner will be responsible for uploading the data sets they have created/collected.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- File name
- Date
- Version
- File type
- Description
- WP number
- Responsible person
- Dissemination level

Instructions for uploading of files to the SINGLE SharePoint Site:

1. Please upload all SINGLE data sets to their corresponding folder in the SINGLE SharePoint site.
2. Use the correct naming convention (for details see 4.1.2).
3. Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions.
4. Add metadata (see list above)

2.2. Open data repository

A community has been created in Zenodo for the SINGLE project. All non-sensitive data, such as scientific publications and underlying data sets, reports and data sets with dissemination level "Public", will be uploaded to the SINGLE community in

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Zenodo. Public deliverables and scientific publications in open access will also be published on the project website <https://single-h2.eu/>.

Instructions for upload files in Zenodo SINGLE community:

1. Create a profile in Zenodo
2. Search “SINGLE-H2 community” under the “Communities” tap at the top of the Zenodo site.
3. On the Community site, click the green "New upload" button in the top right corner
4. Enter requested data and confirm the upload.

Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets created/collected by them. If needed, the Coordinator will supply assistance. Uploading should be done as soon as possible. Scientific articles should be uploaded as soon as possible after publication.

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3. Data summary

SINGLE will collect data of different informative value:

- Experimental data, modelling and simulations, reports about analysis and project results (WP1-4)
- LCA and techno-economic studies, scale-up and business analyses (WP5-6)
- Materials for standardization activities, communication and dissemination (WP7)

Examples of the digital data forms and common file formats are given below:

- Text (e.g. docx, txt, pdf)
- Presentation (e.g. pptx, pdf)
- Numerical (e.g. SPSS, STATA, .xlsx, Access, MySQL, .opju)
- Multimedia (e.g. jpeg, tiff, wav, mpeg, quicktime)
- Models (e.g. 3D, statistical, MPH)
- Software (e.g. Jpy, ipynb, java, C)
- Domain-specific (e.g., CIF in chemistry)

The size of the data will vary but will in total be moderate and should not represent any challenge regarding storage capacity or handling.

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4. FAIR DATA

The SINGLE project works according to the principles of FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) aiming to maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by the project. This does not mean, however, that all data should be 'open'. The basic principle is that data should be open to the public whenever possible and closed when needed. In that sense, there are data sets generated in this project that cannot be shared due to commercial or IPR reasons.

4.1. Making data findable

Zenodo will be used as repository to make the non-sensitive data in SINGLE project findable in accordance with the FAIR data principles. All uploads in Zenodo will by default follow standard Zenodo principles:

4.1.1. Metadata

Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema terms. Each data in Zenodo is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and described with rich metadata:

- Digital Object Identifier
- Publication date
- Authors (Name and ORCID)
- Abstract/description
- Version number
- Language
- Keywords
- Access and licensing info
- Grant information (Grant number, Project Name and Acronym)
- Related project and community
- Associated publications and reports (if any)

4.1.2. Naming conventions

Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

SINGLE_Title_version

where:

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- "SINGLE" is the project's acronym
- "Title" refers to a *short* description of the content of the dataset. In case of deliverables or milestones a deliverable or milestone number as described in the DoA should be included.
- "version" refers to the number version of the file.

Example of dataset name:

SINGLE_D8.3 Data management plan_v1.0

4.1.3. Search keywords

Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets created/collected by them and will be responsible to assign specific search keywords descriptive to the content of the dataset. Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.

4.1.4. Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

All data uploaded on Zenodo are assigned a DOI. The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record. This also allows to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload.

4.2. Making data accessible

All public datasets, scientific publications and public deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo where SINGLE has a community. Data sets with dissemination level sensitive will not be shared due to privacy/security/ethical concerns and they will only be shared with the project contributors in the SINGLE SharePoint. Potentially, some datasets might be restricted due to protection for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be informed in the final version of the DMP.

All data, as publications and underlying data sets, uploaded to Zenodo will be linked through use of DOI. Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the

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web¹. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. No specific software or hardware is needed to access and reuse the data.

All public deliverables and scientific publications in open access will also be available on the SINGLE website <https://single-h2.eu/>. The access to the website and the download of the files will be monitored.

4.3. Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. The data record metadata uses vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.

4.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying license)

The Creative Commons (CC) Attribution licenses will be the standards to be used for all public set of data. Specifically for SINGLE, the recommended license is CC BY 4.0. This license enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use. However, it is important to note that more restrictive licenses as CC BY-SA and CC BY-NC, which do not allow commercial usage, may also be utilized. Partners of the project are required to indicate the license that will be applicable for the data and their related metadata, and this will be assessed in each case.

Depending on their origin, the reference data sets will be made available as soon as possible. The public deliverables will be made available as soon as they are approved and accepted by the EC. For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made as soon as reasonably possible after journal publication.

The public data and metadata be retained for the lifetime of the repository Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an

¹ <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least. Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate from the data itself.

SINGLE quality assurance processes are described in the Quality Plan of SINGLE (D8.2).

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5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Zenodo is a free of charge research data repository. The costs of data management activities are included in the project budget. CTMS is the lead of WP8 and is responsible for the task related to data management *T8.4. Data management*. CTMS will be responsible for the data management and quality assurance.

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6. DATA SECURITY

Data security for all documents uploaded to Zenodo relies on Zenodo's security measures.

Data security for confidential deliverables relies on SharePoint and the DLS infrastructure.

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7. ETHICAL ASPECTS

When submitting a data file, the submitter should confirm that the research data which he/she has submitted does not contain any personal data. If personal data is contained it must be anonymized completely according to canonical standards and the human subjects have consented to the data collection as well as to the publication of the (anonymized) data.

Personal rights: When submitting a data file, the submitter should confirm that by submitting personal metadata (name and surname of the participating person) he/she acts in consent with all persons whose data he/she enters. He/she should also confirm that he/she doesn't violate any personal rights by omitting the name of any participating person.

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8. CONCLUSIONS

This document offers a description of the datasets to be collected and managed within the SINGLE project. It also provides information regarding how these datasets comply with all the FAIR principles. A project community has been opened in Zenodo, which will be the main repository for public, non-sensitive data sets. Sensitive data sets will be uploaded to the project SharePoint.

The data that integrates this DMP must be considered non-personal data, thus being excluded from the application of the GDPR. Main datasets will be related to experimental data, modelling, project results and materials for communication and dissemination. The potential public dissemination of the datasets that will be collected/generated inside the project will be evaluated case by case, restricting access at only the internal level of intellectual property or privacy reasons are invoked by a partner.

Partners are aware that this document is not the final version of SINGLE DMP, and commit to update this content in the following version.

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